

Study on World Rowing Championships Economic Impact

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Introduction

In 2014 FISA (The International Rowing Federation), Sport2B and the Amsterdam University of Applied Sciences (AUAS) started an international partnership focused on further developing FISA's knowledge about the local and regional impact of its major events. As part of this partnership a study was carried out on the economic impact of the 2015 WRCH in Aiguebelette, France. This study is focused on the impact of the Championships on a pre-defined area - the Lake Aiguebelette Area. The economic impact of the event is defined by the additional spending of various parties, i.e. visitors, athletes and their staff, LOC, media representatives, etc.

Methods

To determine the spending by local, national and international visitors, insights from the visitor survey were used carried part of the LOC's own economic impact study. During the event 605 visitors were interviewed about their spending behavior. Using a standard questionnaire the researchers collected information on various relevant issues, i.e. place of residence, reason of visit, length of visit, average daily spending, number of overnight stays, type of accommodation, price of overnight stays, etc. To determine spending by athletes, their staff and officials, information from the LOC was used about the number and location of overnight stays, price of accommodation and average daily spending.

Results

Accommodation and daytime spending by visitors of the 2015 WRCH added up to a positive impact of €1,333,000 on the Lake Aiguebelette area economy. Total spending by athletes, their staff and officials added up to a positive impact of €3,229,000, the LOC - €836,000 and media representatives - €138,000 on the Lake Aiguebelette area economy.

Overall, the 2015 WRCH had a positive impact on the Lake Aiguebelette area economy. Over a period of eight days the event generated almost 19,300 additional overnight stays in the area. Local spending by visitors,

athletes and staff, media-representatives and the LOC added up to a positive impact of €5.5 million on the local economy.

References

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